

METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH MEDICAL STUDENTS

Esanova Maftuna Bakhodirovna

Assistant-teacher of the department of Languages, Samarkand State Medical University

Doliev Khondamir Ravshanovich

First year student of the Faculty of General Medicine, Samarkand State Medical University

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Abstract. The modern world needs competent and mobile medical professionals who can work in a multicultural society anywhere in the world. The purpose of this work is to determine the structure and content of the “Foreign Language” discipline, which would contribute to a more conscious, active and motivated learning of the subject. The methodology of the research was federal state educational standards, programs of the discipline “Foreign Language” for higher educational institutions and existing literature on the research problem. The purpose of this article is to identify the most common difficulties faced by teachers of English for specific purposes in the teaching process and to provide them with possible solutions to these problems.

Key words: language proficiency, sound problematic, different levels, self-development, healthcare systems, group and pair work, collaborative learning, role-playing games, mini-projects, sociocultural differences.

Introduction. In teaching a foreign language at different levels, the project method is actively used; higher medical institutions are no exception. The project method touches on various aspects, namely, in addition to mastering educational material, it promotes the development of creative potential, teaches how to systematize acquired knowledge, analyze information, navigate the information flow, and activates the ability to work independently and in teams. However, there are a number of rules that must be followed in order for the project method to be effective; in particular, the subject of the project is always should sound problematic, in the process of working on the project, the types of activities of students should vary, the results of the project should have practical, educational and theoretical significance.

Another approach currently widely used in vocationally oriented training is Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL). The role of a foreign language in CLIL is unique because it acts not only as a goal, but also as a means of teaching almost any discipline.

Having studied the theoretical information on the problem and the empirical data obtained during the survey, we determined that a foreign language course for medical students should consist of three main modules. In the first year, students should focus on learning general medical vocabulary and oral communication. Next, they improve medical terminology and read professional texts. At the third stage, students learn to produce their texts and present them at conferences. Agreeing with researchers that at the beginning of the course it is often necessary to fill gaps in school knowledge, and mastering professional vocabulary occurs in the absence of knowledge in the subject of the specialty, we propose to distribute the “Foreign Language” discipline over three years with a gradual increase in complexity. Separate modules should be added to the existing number of hours in the first

year in the second and third (fourth) years of study. Some authors note a decrease in motivation for learning a foreign language among the majority of students when moving to senior years, however, we explain this fact by the fact that not all future doctors connect their careers with scientific activities that require active language proficiency.

Results and discussion. Several methods can be used to identify needs, for example: interviews, questionnaires, observations, etc. The source for needs analysis can be students, teachers, etc. It is important to find out not only information about what students expect from English classes, but also to monitor the environment in which students will speak English.

If the learners are university students, they will need to develop listening skills to understand lectures and seminars develop writing skills to write projects or dissertations, develop speaking skills to give oral presentations, etc. If a student needs a foreign language for present or future work, then the teacher must find out what kind of work it is and what area of knowledge in the language will be required in the future.

It is generally accepted that teaching English for specific purposes should be tailored to the needs of language learners. In terms of teaching English for medical purposes, the main needs of medical students include understanding cited texts about the latest developments in medical science, practice and improving conversational (speaking) skills with an emphasis on mastering medical terminology through role-play, paired and teamwork, projects. In addition, practicing writing skills in the form of presenting thematic reports, research, and preparing medical documentation is also useful. In addition, medical students should have the opportunity to keep up with relevant literature, write scientific papers, and participate in student exchanges and international student congresses. This form of activity provides a solid basis that allows them to exchange knowledge and experience with foreign colleagues, as well as publish scientific articles in reputable international journals.

The third module, intended for those planning scientific and grant activities, can also be elective.

Figure 1 - Model of the "Foreign Language" course at a medical university

As the basis of the module, we take situations of language use that are focused on the learning outcome, determine their thematic content and the necessary language tools (vocabulary and grammatical structures). The second and third modules are also focused on developing skills in various types of speech activity and involve teaching autonomy and self-development. As a teaching method, a combination of forms and methods used in professionally oriented and subject-language integrated training is proposed.

Table 1 - Modular structure of the Foreign Language course

Module 1 Basic medical terminology (1 year of study)

The goal is to develop communicative and intercultural competencies

Situations: patient - hospital receptionist, doctor - patient (patient's relatives).

Topics: calling a doctor, making an appointment, health and symptoms of illness, patient examination, diagnosis, medical history, healthcare systems and sociocultural differences in different countries.

Vocabulary body parts, physical condition, well-being, illnesses, injuries, accidents, symptoms, hygiene, medications.

Grammar interrogative sentences, Simple, Continuous, Perfect tenses, degrees of comparison of adjectives and adverbs, modal verbs.

Forms and methods: group and pair work, collaborative learning, role-playing games, mini-projects.

Module 2 Reading professional literature (2nd year of study).

The goal is the formation of communicative and intercultural competencies and the ability to build and implement a trajectory of self-development based on the principles of lifelong education.

Situations doctor - doctor, doctor - patient (patient's relatives)

Topics for discussion of treatment, types of dictionaries, strategies for teaching reading, methods of extracting and processing information for the purpose of its further use, abstract, abstract.

Vocabulary of the disease, symptoms, treatment methods, medications

Participle grammar, participial phrases, infinitive and its constructions, passive voice, phrasal verbs, abbreviations.

Forms and methods: group and pair work, collaborative learning, translation and analysis of texts, use of cases, mini-projects.

Module 3 Creating your own texts and oral presentation (3/4 year of study).

The goal is the formation of communicative and intercultural competencies and the ability to build and implement a trajectory of self-development based on the principles of lifelong education.

Situations: doctor - doctor, doctor - clinic director (employer), doctor - scientific director, doctor - conference organizer, doctor - journal editor.

Topics: grant, resume, motivation letter, business letter, conference abstracts, presentation, speech, article about research results, correspondence with the editor, strategies for teaching writing and oral presentation.

Vocabulary professional and academic.

Grammar - grammatical structures characteristic of oral and written communication style on the topic being studied.

Forms and methods: discussion, brainstorming, collaborative learning, mini-projects, business and role-playing games, situation modeling.

Some strategies to ensure balanced practice of these skills include improving constructive dialogue between faculty and students, collaborating with core course instructors, and ongoing assessment to create an appropriate curriculum designed specifically for health care professionals. The special relationship between teachers and students has a good influence on teaching methods and stimulates the student [4]. Moreover, long-term learning is the foundation of higher education, and as equal partners, both students and teachers must recognize that education is a two-way process.

Conclusion. In summary, our study showed that the objectives of teaching English for medical purposes and the minimum level of specific skills are not clearly defined. The results of the study also showed that students lack speaking skills. The authors of the study offered recommendations for improving oral communication skills, which will allow students to communicate successfully in the professional field. It should also be noted that there is a need for closer cooperation between teachers, as this will contribute to improving the quality of teaching and student achievement.

Medical English training should focus not only on vocabulary acquisition and text analysis, but also on developing communication skills, problem solving, and decision making. Teachers of

English for Specific Purposes should recognize the need to introduce and develop so-called critical thinking skills in their students so that they can meet both professional and social demands. Teaching English to medical students is not merely about language instruction; it is about equipping future healthcare professionals with the tools to communicate effectively, empathetically, and ethically. The journey toward English proficiency is complex, but the rewards are profound. By addressing the linguistic, cultural, high-stakes, methodological, and ethical challenges, educators and institutions can ensure that medical students are not only proficient in language but also culturally sensitive, ethical, and patient-centered healthcare providers.

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